

Appendix: Post study survey questions

This table shows the post study survey question and how we divided them in to different groups.

Code	Survey Question	Answer Type
FAIRNESS_1	I feel that the system respected my input and choices.	Scale (1-7)
FAIRNESS_2	The recommendations reflected the preferences I set using the sliders.	Scale (1-7)
FAIRNESS_3	I felt that my fairness and diversity settings had a noticeable effect on the recommendations.	Scale (1-7)
FAIRNESS_4	I felt listened to by the system.	Scale (1-7)
FAIRNESS_5	Adjusting diversity and fairness settings led to recommendations that felt more related to my preference.	Scale (1-7)
CONTROL_1	I felt in control of how the recommendations were generated.	Scale (1-7)
CONTROL_2	The sliders made it easy to express what I wanted from the recommendations.	Scale (1-7)
CONTROL_3	I understood how my slider settings influenced the results.	Scale (1-7)
CONTROL_4	It felt like the recommendations were a result of my input.	Scale (1-7)
CONTROL_5	Using the sliders gave me more trust in the recommendation process.	Scale (1-7)
CONTROL_6	I felt more satisfied because I had a say in the level of diversity in my recommendations.	Scale (1-7)
VALUE_1	This approach to setting fairness preferences improved my listening experience.	Scale (1-7)
VALUE_2	Having these kinds of options helped me reflect on what I value in music discovery.	Scale (1-7)
VALUE_3	I would prefer a recommender system if it allowed me to adjust fairness settings like this.	Scale (1-7)
CURRENT_1	I feel like current music recommendation apps treat me fairly.	Scale (1-7)
CURRENT_2	I feel I have control over the music that gets recommended to me by music recommender apps.	Scale (1-7)
IMPORTANCE_1	Which fairness dimensions were most important to you while using the sliders?	Categories